

Suggestopedia : Development of English Language Skills

Harish R

Assistant Professor,
Deptt. of Education,
KSEF College of Education,
Northern Extn, Tumkur

Abstract

Suggestopedia is a set of learning reconstruction based on scientific method with non rational non coconsciousness influences and also it direct the student not you vocabulary memorization and acquiring study habits of speech and also to act of communication in this method it includes 6 principles they are authority infantilization double plandness intonation rhythm pseudo passiveness and meanwhile in learning and teaching activity develops imitations, questions and answer and role play also here the role of the teacher in to be confident fastidious conduct and good attitude finally this method received both the enthusiastic and most crucial response in teaching and learning of language English.

Keywords: Suggests, Non Rational, Lozanov, Infantilization, Intonation, Rhythm.

Introduction

Suggestopedia is a method of teaching English. It is developed by the Bulgarian psychiatrist-educator Georgi Lozanov Suggestopedia is a specific set of learning recommendations derived from suggestology suggestology means science concerned with the systematic study of the nonrational and no conscious influences.

The most conspicuous characteristics of suggestopedia are the decoration, furniture and arrangement of the class room, the use of music and the authoritative behavior of the teacher.

The claims for suggestopedia learning are dramatic. "There is no sector of public life where suggestology build not be useful". These are the lines quoted by Lozanov in 1978.

The most conspicuous feature of suggestopedia is the centrality of music and musical rhythm to learning.

One of the earliest attested uses of music therapy is recorded In the Old Testament of the Bible: "When the evil spirit from god was upon Saul, David took up his harp and played with his hand : so Saul found relief: and it was will with him, and the evil spirit departed from him". Lozana' might have described this incident to show the greatness of music. Gaston (1968) defines three functions of music.

They are-

1. To facilitate the establishment
2. Maintenance of personal relationships.
3. Increased self-esteem through increased self satisfaction.

Use of unique potential of rhythm to energize and bring order. Suggestopedic course directs that "the student not to vocabulary memorization and acquiring habits of speech, but to acts of communication". Lozanov recommends home study of recording of "whole meaningful texts". That are, "above all interesting". They are listened to "for the sake of the music of the foreign language".

There are six principle theoretical components through which desuggestion and suggestion operate and that set up access to resents. They are,

Authority

Lozanov dictates a variety of prescriptions and prescriptions aimed at having suggestopedia students experience the educational establishment and the teacher as sources having great authority. Lozanov talks of choosing a 'ritual placebo system' that are most likely to be perceived of by students as having high authority.

Infantilization

In the Childs role the learner takes part in role playing, games, songs, and gymnastic exercises. That help "the older student regain the self-confidence, spontaneity and receptivity of the child".

Double-Plandness

The bright decor of the class room, the musical background, the shape of the chairs, and the personality of the teacher are considered as important in instruction as the form of the instructional material itself.

Intonation Rhythm

Both intonation and rhythm are coordinated with a musical background.

Pseudo-Passiveness

The musical background helps to induce a relaxed attitude which Lozanov refers to as a concert pseudo passiveness.

Suggestopedia apparently bases its learning claims on student mastery of prodigious lists of vocabulary pairs and, indeed, suggests to the students that it is appropriate that they set such goals for themselves.

Learning and teaching activities in suggestopedia include imitation, question and answer, and role play- which are not activities 'that other language teachers' would consider to be out of the ordinary. The type of activities that are more original to suggestopedia are the listening activities, which concern the texts and text vocabulary of each unit

Student volunteer for a Suggestopedic course, but having volunteered they are expected to be committed to the class and its activities. Students are expected to tolerate and in fact encourage their own infantilization.

Aim of the Study

To develop specific set of learning recommendations through science concern with non rational and non conscious influences with the authoritative behavior towards potential of rhythm and dramatic senses to maintain increased self-esteem through increased self satisfaction.

Teacher Roles

1. Show absolute confident in the method.
2. Display fastidious conduct in manners and dress.
3. Maintain a solemn attitude towards the session.
4. Give tests and respond tactfully to poor papers.
5. Stress global rather than analytical attitudes towards material.
6. Maintain a modest enthusiasm, consists of direct support materials, tape, and indirect support materials, fixtures and music.

Bancroft notes that the four-hour language class has three distinct parts.

The first part we might call an oral review section. Previously learned material is used as the basis for discussion by the teacher and twelve students in the class.

The second part of the class new material is discussed. This consists of looking over and its native language translation and issues of grammar vocabulary or content.

The-third part the séance or concert session- is the one by which suggestopedia is best unknown.

Since this constitutes the heart of the method, we will quote Lozanov as to hen this session proceeds.

Suggestopedia has probably received both the most enthusiastic and the most critical response of any of the so called new methods.

A poem from the text 9 SW. which we can teach under this suggestopedia. i.e. "The Daffodils".

When the poet says:

I wandered lonely as a cloud

That floats on high over vales & hills.

Here the teacher acts himself to show how the poet wandered, and he can show clouds, by acting how they floats over vales & hills.

When the poet says,

Daffodils are the twinkling stars on the Milky Way.

Teacher can show how the stars twinkle.

The poet says, suddenly I saw ten thousand daffodils!

Here we can make use of some musical background which creates wonder.

We can also make use of background music that indicates the breeze is blowing. When the poet says the daffodils were dancing in a cold breeze,

When the teacher says 'when I am in pensive mood I remember daffodils.'

Here the teacher acts like a melancholic person and suddenly he thought some thing and enjoyed it.

Like this we can teach this poem under this teaching method Suggestopedia.

Conclusion

The present system of education progressing towards new and modern methods in the incorporation of various types of skills, techniques, methods and approaches in the same way teaching for the language English is also dealt with the method suggestopedia in learning of classroom English to enhance the spirit of musical rhythm and to develop a systematic study of decoration based on the aesthetic sense of English. It also initiates for the double plandness and intonations with pseudo passiveness also. It directs towards listening activities in a systematic way especially in learning of language English.

References

1. *Teaching of English – S.K. Mangal, 1991 Vol- 2, Neel Kamal Publications, Agra.*
2. *Teaching of Language Bhatia and Bhatia, Himalaya Publications, Ludiyana – 1998.*
3. *Teaching of English – Unnathi Basanthi, Tendan Publications, Delhi- 1992 Vol 3A. Edutrack, Research Review*
4. *Research innovations in languages –Vismaya prakashana 2013, vol-1, Mysore*
5. *NCERT Text book for B.Ed syllabus teaching of languages 2014 Government Press New Delhi*
6. *Teaching of English vol-2, Vismaya prakashana Dr. S P Padmaprasad, Mysore*